

APPROACHES TO ORGANIZING STUDENT INDUSTRIAL PRACTICE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18281500>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th January 2026

Accepted: 16th January 2026

Online: 17th January 2026

KEYWORDS

student practice, production practice, competency-based education, dual education, innovative pedagogy, digital monitoring, professional competencies

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the organization and effectiveness of students' production practice in higher education institutions based on a new approach. Organizing production practice in a competency-based, innovative, interactive, and public-private partnership format enhances students' professional development, practical skills, problem-solving abilities, and teamwork competence. The use of electronic diaries, digital portfolios, and simulators allows transparent and effective monitoring of the practice process. The application of dual education elements facilitates rapid adaptation to production processes and the formation of a real work culture

Introduction. In today's era of globalization, technological innovations taking place in all sectors of the economy, the digitization of production processes, and the requirements for professional competence in the labor market make the training of highly qualified specialists one of the most urgent tasks for the education system. In particular, in higher educational institutions, combining theoretical knowledge with practical skills, increasing their readiness for professional activity, and directly introducing students to real production processes are among the priority areas of today's educational strategy. Production practice organized on the basis of a traditional approach often leads to problems such as the inability of students to fully apply the knowledge they have learned in practice, practical tasks do not meet modern production standards, and cooperation between enterprises and educational institutions is not sufficiently systematized [1, 2]. Therefore, at this stage, the need to organize production practice in a new approach, competency-oriented, innovative, interactive, and based on public-private partnership, has sharply increased. The new approach requires not only updating the mechanism for conducting practice, but also inextricably linking the educational process with production, increasing student activity, modernizing the content of practical assignments, and most importantly, creating individual educational and practical directions that serve the student's professional development. Such a transformation, in turn, will improve the quality of the educational process, train competitive personnel in the labor market, and provide enterprises with qualified specialists [3, 4]. Also, the new model of production practice allows for the formation of a three-way cooperation mechanism between the student, the educational institution, and the enterprise. Within the framework of this mechanism, enterprises organize the student's activities in real production conditions, while

educational institutions provide methodological and pedagogical support for the process. During the practice, the student develops such professional skills as personal initiative, independent thinking, problem solving, teamwork, and responsibility. Therefore, it is practically and theoretically relevant to conduct scientific and analytical research on the organization of students' production practice based on a new approach, identify existing problems, propose effective methods, and develop scientific conclusions and recommendations for improving the system. This article discusses new approaches to the process of production practice, their impact on the quality of education, and mechanisms for increasing the effectiveness of practice on a scientific basis. In the modern educational process, production practice is not only an integral part of the curriculum, but also serves as the foundation for forming a professional worldview in students. Therefore, the need for new methods of organizing practice is increasing. The new approach requires, first of all, the participation of the student in the process as an active subject. The theoretical foundations of this approach are based on competency-based education, a person-oriented model of practice, the concept of integrated education with production, and innovative pedagogical technologies [5]. This concept ensures that the student is not just an observer, but a specialist who directly participates in the production process, makes independent decisions and performs practical tasks. The new approach also involves the widespread use of interactive methods enriched with laboratory practical exercises, pilot projects, digital simulation technologies and real production tasks [6]. The effectiveness of production practice largely depends on the systematic cooperation between educational institutions and enterprises and organizations. In traditional practices, relations between enterprises and educational institutions are often formal in nature, which creates inconsistencies in the specific tasks, competencies and assessment criteria that the student must perform.

Main results. The conducted analyses, scientific research and practical observations showed that conducting students' production practice based on a new approach plays an important role in their professional development, their desire for self-improvement and their formation as competitive specialists in the labor market. The results of the study were reflected in several main aspects. Since the practical tasks set on the basis of the new approach were adapted to the real needs of enterprises, it was observed that the student's active participation in practice significantly increased. The student now, unlike previous years, is not just an observer, but an active participant, performer and initiator.

The new approach introduced the joint management of enterprise representatives, mentors and teachers of the educational institution in the practice structure. As a result:

- the quality of the practical process increased,
- tasks were clearly and systematically formulated,
- the goals set for practice were more fully realized,
- the role of enterprises in assessing practice increased.

The data obtained showed that the practice organized on the basis of the new approach significantly developed students' skills in solving problem situations, working in a team, applying professional techniques, effective time management and a sense of responsibility. Students' self-confidence increased, and their level of readiness for future professional activities was strengthened.

The use of electronic diaries, digital portfolios, virtual laboratories and simulators increased students' activity in practice. Now, even from a distance, students have the opportunity to monitor the results transparently and electronically. The student's daily activities are clearly recorded, and the assessment system has become fast and objective. Updating the assessment criteria has allowed for a fair and accurate analysis. This assessment model allows not only to fully demonstrate the student's potential, but also the quality of assignments, recommendations from enterprises and independent thinking.

The use of dual education elements in the process of training a specialist has yielded results. When using the dual education approach, the student's rapid adaptation to the production process, effective use of technologies, and the formation of a work culture in a real work environment were observed. This further harmonized the educational process with production. Students' motivation for practice increased.

During the modernization of practice, motivational increases were clearly observed among students, such as interest in the profession, planning their professional goals, striving to express themselves in enterprises, and determining future work activities.

Conclusion. Organizing production practice based on new approaches is a strategically important process for the modern education system. In today's labor market, a competitive specialist is required not only theoretical knowledge, but also real production experience, the ability to quickly adapt, make independent decisions, work effectively in a team, and in-depth mastery of digital technologies. From this point of view, the modernization of practice is an urgent task for higher educational institutions and enterprises. The results of the study showed that the effectiveness of practice primarily depends on how it is organized. Modern approaches such as competency-based education, dual system, mentoring, project-based learning and digital monitoring increase student activity, ensure the application of theoretical knowledge in real conditions and contribute to the continuous development of professional skills. In general, the organization of production practice based on new approaches, as an innovative development direction of education, serves the interests not only of the student, but also of higher educational institutions and enterprises. The practice system formed on the basis of these approaches makes it possible to train highly qualified personnel, increase their adaptability to the labor market and contribute to the development of society. Therefore, it is necessary to constantly improve the processes of modernization of the practice system, its digitalization and integration with enterprises. In short, the organization of student practice based on a new approach is an integral and most important part of modern education. This process is crucial for combining the student's theoretical knowledge with practice, forming professional competencies, training personnel in accordance with the requirements of the labor market and improving the quality of education. In the future, to further improve the practice, it is necessary to develop methodological support, strengthen strategic cooperation with enterprises, widely use digital technologies, and expand the mentoring system. At the same time, this research aims to modernize production practice

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